

RESEARCH ON THE SYNTHESIS OF ORGANIC ADDITIVES THAT INCREASE THE OCTANE NUMBER OF GASOLINE WHICH CONTAINING NITROGEN AND OXYGEN

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Abstract. In this paper, we have conducted on obtain new types of organic additives in order to improve the number of octane for gasoline Which containing oxygen and nitrogen. All of them synthesized based on the follow chemical compounds, triacetin (TA), diisooamyl phthalate ether (DIAP), N-methylaniline (NMA), isoamyl acetate (IAA), isopropanol alcohol (IPA), methyl alcohol (MS) and urotropine. The results showed that, the effect of additives on the concentration of toxic gases emitted into the air as a result of combustion in the engine was studied by compounding with local low-octane gasoline and its various fractions.

Keywords: organic additive, poisonous gas, gas analyzer, gasoline, oxygenate.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В нашей научно-исследовательской работе мы испытали несколько органических добавок для повышения октанового числа бензина, содержащих кислород и азот. В их основе: триацетин (ТА), диизоамилфталатный эфир (ДИАФ), N-метиланилин (ММА), изоамилацетат (ИАА), изопропаноловый спирт (ИПС), метиловый спирт (МС) и уротропин. При этом влияние присадок на концентрацию токсичных газов, выбрасываемых в воздух в результате сгорания в двигателе, изучалось путем компаундирования с местным низкооктановым бензином и его различными фракциями.

Ключевые слова: органическая добавка, ядовитый газ, газоанализатор, бензин, оксигенат.

Introduction. In our rapidly changing world, to improve the environmental and operational properties of gasoline is the use of multifunctional additives, mainly oxygenates, oxygen-containing substances (alcohols, ketones, simple and complex ethers, etc.). The presence of oxygen in the fuel makes it possible to reduce harmful emissions of carbon monoxide by

30%, and unburned hydrocarbons by 15% [1,2]. With the acceleration of the development of automobile production, the number of cars is increasing, which is the reason for the formation of traffic jams on the streets. This, in its turn, leads to a massive increase in the amount of toxic smoke emitted from cars, which has a harmful effect on human health and the environment. In the exhaust contains about 220 harmful substances, including carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbon (CH), nitric oxide (NO_x) and other gases. A lot of types of danger chemical compounds may lead to seriously nefative effect for human health: carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, which have a negative effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems. At the current time, the car emits up to 1 kg of exhaust gases[3,4].

In this research has been studied, testing processes for determining the concentration of exhaust gases released into the air as a result of combustion of high-octane gasoline samples obtained in the engine by compounding local low-octane gasoline with nitrogen and oxygen-containing organic additives were carried out in the scientific laboratory of the Tashkent City Department of the Ministry of Natural Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The test procedures were carried out on a five-component INFRAKAR 5M-3T.01 brand gas analyzer in accordance with GOST 17.2.2.03-87.

Table 1

Concentration of exhaust gases released into the air as a result of combustion of gasoline samples compounded with organic additives containing nitrogen and oxygen

The name of component	The amount of additives	N _{min}				N _{max}			
		CO	CO ₂	CH	O ₂ /NO _x	CO	CO ₂	CH	O ₂ /NO _x
AI-80	-	0,26	14,69	074	0,35/047	1,32	13,67	225	1,05/135
MMA	1,3%	0,08	14,95	070	0,21/042	0,86	13,92	185	0,71/114
TA	5%	0,00	15,94	058	0,18/035	0,72	15,34	152	0,52/091
HMK-5	5%	0,04	14,82	072	0,22/049	0,82	14,65	170	0,61/122
TME-4	10%	0,00	16,00	050	0,16/030	0,60	15,60	130	0,48/080

		0	2	2	2	7	9	5	3
MT	5%	0,0	15,6	06	0,20/03	0,7	14,5	16	0,65/09
		0	7	2	8	9	2	2	8
HM-3	2,5%	0,0	14,6	07	0,25/05	0,9	13,8	17	0,74/13
		6	6	5	0	5	0	6	1

Figure 1. Changes in the concentration of CO % released into the air as a result of the combustion of gasoline samples compounded with organic additives containing nitrogen and oxygen

Figure 2. Changes in the CH ppm indicator of air emissions due to engine combustion of gasoline samples compounded with nitrogen and oxygen-containing organic additives

In this research have been tested a process of determining the concentration of waste gases released into the air in the five-component INFRAKAR 5M-3T.01 gas-analyzer system according to GOST 17.2.2.03-87 standard, additives of different concentrations were added to the used gasoline samples according to the norms of Oz DSt 3031-2015. A gasoline sample of AI-80 brand (reformatted and directly driven), when passed through a gas analyzer, showed CO-0.26%, CO₂-14.69%, CH-74ppm, NO_x-47ppm and non-combustion O₂-0.35% in Nmin is

determined to be equal to In Nmax, CO-1.32%, CO₂-13.67%, CH-225ppm, NO_x-135ppm, and non-combustion O₂-1.05% were shown. Among the waste gases, the most toxic and characteristic are CO and CH. In the analysis of waste gases, changes in concentrations at Nmax are presented. The MMA additive reduced CO by 0.46% and CH by 40ppm when added to AI-80 gasoline at 1.3% at Nmax. Adding 5% of TA brand oxygen scavenger reduced CO concentration by 0.6% and CH concentration by 73 ppm. Adding 5% of HMK-5 oxygen and nitrogen storage additive reduced CO concentration by 0.5% and CH concentration by 55 ppm. Addition of 10% TME-4 oxygen scavenging additive reduced CO concentration by 0.65% and CH concentration by 90 ppm. The addition of 5% of MT brand oxygen and nitrogen storage additive reduced CO concentration by 0.53% and CH concentration by 63 ppm. Adding 2.5% of HM-3 nitrogen-fixing additive reduced CO by 0.37% and CH by 49 ppm.

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